

PECULIARITIES OF METAPHOR AND SIMILE IN BUSINESS LANGUAGE

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Faculty of foreign philosophy

Department of English Linguistics

student of Master's degree

Ernazarova Madinakhon Bakhtiyor kizi

Annotation: The article deeply analyzed the topic contrastive study of Metaphor and simile in English and Uzbek economic terms. Furthermore, usage of metaphor in economics, Conceptual metaphors and their main tasks were highlighted.

Key words: *rhetoric, dominant, anthropomorphic, voting metaphor, democratic, fundamental value, stockbrokers, conceptual metaphors.*

The prevalence of metaphors within the realm of business rhetoric is notable; nonetheless, this phenomenon has been largely disregarded in theoretical discourse. One potential explanation for this disregard stems from business officials's lack of awareness when engaging in rhetoric. Most economists may say that they have never heard of metaphor and that it should be avoided in scientific language because it is an instrument of imprecision, though they are unconsciously using it daily. According to one of the famous writer, John Kay, views market as an "anthropomorphic and voting metaphor". [1] Two types of metaphor were described by him: "The anthropomorphic metaphor is hierarchical. „We might ask the market“ City folk will say, but only if they occupy very senior positions or are leading specialists in their field. Such individuals are privileged

by direct access to Mr. Market himself. The most discreetly influential figures in the city and on Wall Street display the style and mannerisms of Mr. Market's courtiers. The voting metaphor is democratic. Everybody's point of view counts although some opinions count for more than others. Views are weighted by the amount of money behind them ..." [2].

Market are defined by Kay as "a silly old fool who occasionally makes assets available to Berkshire Hathaway beyond their fundamental value." It was observed that the whole text is highly metaphorical (relying mainly on personification), seasoned with sarcasm and irony. Of course, we wouldn't expect an article on an economic issue to be subjective, to abound in figures of speech, but here it should be taken into account the journalistic style. Market is, indeed, one of the most used metaphors in business texts. It is actually traders and stockbrokers who exert their energy buying and selling and who use their financial expertise to take risks in the pursuit of profit. However, as Mason said that: "human characteristics are frequently transferred from these people to the market in general, or specific aspects of it". In arrange to support all given above, we should give attention to this text[3] , a very rich source of material for analysis:

- *Brokers said the market was having trouble focusing on issues which could give it direction.*

In the thought and being considered basic and universal process the conceptual metaphors plays significant role. They are display within the major occasions of human counting exchange, birth, death, sex, etc. They are common and abstract, and belong to dead metaphors, so that one is not aware of them, at all. The more important and individual they are, the more likely it is for them to acquire cultural connotations, thus representing a certain community. Far from being an ornamental literary device, metaphor is seen as pervading everyday

patterns of discourse and being essential to thought and understanding. Many writers now make a distinction between conceptual and linguistic metaphor, whereby metaphor exists in mind, as a connection between two semantic areas[4], while the metaphorical lexis used in text is merely the conceptual metaphor's linguistic or surface realisation. Thus, the economy as a whole is sometimes conceptualised as a living organism or as a person being referred to in terms of strong/weak economy, economic growth/development, economic cycle etc. Economic variables, which increase and decrease are often conceptualised as living organisms that fall, recover, grow, rise, mature, slip back. It was noted by Lakoff and Johnson that human thought is largely metaphorical and metaphorical language is only possible because of the deeper metaphors that exist in our conceptual system[5].

Time is Money one of the famous examples are given by them and from the word money they include related expressions that are utilized to portray time, such as: to afford the time to (I'm busy at work. I can't afford more than a week off at a time), to budget time (I have to budget my time very well if I want to finish until the end of the week.), to save time (Let's get a taxi. It'll save at least 20 minutes.), to value time (Employees have to learn to value their time if they want to finish earlier.), to waste time (We're wasting time waiting for the applicants to come.), to run out of time (The manager ran out of time so he failed in meeting the deadline for the project.), to make time to (The government has to make time to solve the environmental problem as soon as possible.), to spend time (He spent his life working for the poor.), to be short of time (I think we should hurry up. We are short of time.), to borrow time (This government is living on borrowed time.) etc. In the period of the Industrial Revolution the metaphor came into the English language, when individuals began to be paid for work by the amount of time they worked. Hence, the plant driven to the institutional pairing of periods of time with amounts of money, which formed the experiential basis of

this metaphor. Since then, the metaphor has been realized in numerous other ways. The budgeting of time has spread all through American culture.

REFERENCES:

1. Kay, John (2007). Fools fight for favour in the court of Mr. Market, in Financial Times, Tuesday, July, 24, 2007, p.11.
2. Cf. Mason, Mary (1990). Dancing on air: Analysis of a passage from an economics textbook, in Dudley-Evans and Henderson (eds.), pp.16-28.
3. www.financialtimes.com
4. Cf. Deignan et al., Teaching Metaphors using Cross-Linguistic Awareness-Raising Activities in ETL Journal, vol. 51, p. 45. [14]
5. Cf. Lakoff, George, Mark Johnson (1980). Metaphors We live By, Chicago and London, University of Chicago Press, p. 3.